

“HAZARDOUS” FOOD ADDITIVES

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Abstract. The article provides detailed information on one of the current issues, food additives that are permitted and prohibited, preservatives and antioxidants allowed in food products.

Introduction. Food additives are natural or synthetic substances that are not assimilated as nutrients. Their purpose in food products is to extend shelf life, maintain appearance, and modify organoleptic properties. Examples of food additives include various preservatives, colorants, and antioxidants. Currently, due to the high level of additives added to food, the number of gastrointestinal diseases is increasing year by year. Notably, in Europe half a century ago, in 1953, hazardous substances of this type were brought under complete control, and in 1953, these products were coded with the “E” code and a number. In the most developed countries, the use of some of these substances in the food industry is strictly prohibited.

Main Part. Nutritional additives are mainly added to food products for the following purposes:

- to improve the processing, packaging, and storage of raw materials;
- to maintain natural quality indicators;
- to enhance the organoleptic properties, texture, and stability;
- nutritional additives are divided into several groups:
 - substances that improve the structure of food (colorants, color stabilizers, whiteners);
 - flavor-modifying substances (flavoring agents, sweeteners, acids);
 - substances that control product consistency and form hardness (thickeners, gelling agents, emulsifiers, etc.);

• substances that extend the product’s natural state and shelf life (preservatives, antioxidants, etc.).

Currently, there are over 500 additives used in food products. Based on numerical coding, food additives are classified as follows:

1. E100-E182 – colorants;
2. E200-E299 – preservatives;
3. E300-E399 – antioxidants;
4. E400-E499 – stabilizing agents for thickness;
5. E450 and E449, E1000 – emulsifiers;
6. E500-E599 – acidity regulators, softeners;
7. E600-E699 – flavor and aroma enhancers;
8. E700-E800 – reserve indexes;
9. E900 and beyond – bread improvers.

Table-1

Preservatives Permitted for Use in Food Products

	Preservative name	Chemical formula of preservative	Preservative code
.	Sorbic acid		E200
.	Sodium sorbate		E201
.	Potassium sorbate		E202

.	Calcium sorbate		E203
.	Benzoic acid		E210
.	Sodium benzoate		E211
.	Potassium benzoate		E212
.	Calcium benzoate		E213

Nutritional Antioxidants

Nutritional antioxidants primarily include substances that slow down the oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids in lipids. According to their technological function, these additives are divided into three classes: antioxidants, synergistic antioxidants, and complex-forming agents.

Table-2

Nutritional antioxidants

No	Antioxidants	Code
1.	Ascorbic acid	E200
2.	Sodium ascorbate	E301
3.	Calcium ascorbate	E302
4.	Potassium ascorbate	E202
5.	Ascorbyl palmitate	E304
6.	Tocopherol concentrate	E306

7.	Alpha-tocopherol	E307
8.	Delta-tocopherol (Synthetic)	E309
9.	Propyl gallate	E310
10.	Octyl gallate	E311
11.	Dodecyl gallate	E312
12.	Guaiac resin	E314
13.	Isoascorbic acid	E315
14.	Sodium isoascorbate	E316
15.	Potassium isoascorbate	E317

Some Hazardous Food Additives

While some food additives provide an attractive appearance, appeal, and sweet taste to products, they can be very harmful to health. For example, antioxidants like E338 - E341 can cause gastrointestinal issues, while E226, E221-224, and E211-213 additives can lead to intestinal disorders. Colorants like E171-173, used in carbonated drinks, colored ice creams, and candies, can cause kidney and liver diseases. Preservatives such as E240, E210-211, and E213-E217 are used in canned foods, mushrooms, and juices and may contribute to the growth of harmful tumors. Additives like E103, E105, E121, E123, E125, E126, E130, E131, E142, and E153 contain high amounts of colorants, which at high concentrations can lead to malignant tumors. Antioxidants like E311 - E313 and E221 - E226, used in making chocolate, sausages, butter, yogurt, and other dairy products, can cause various gastrointestinal illnesses. Preservatives such as E239 and E230 - E232 can trigger various allergic diseases. Highly dangerous food additives include E513, E123, E527, and E510, which, unfortunately, are still used in the food industry.

References

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